

Cultural Affordances and the Globalization/Localization Dilemma

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Abstract: Continued globalization and the need to localize materials for diverse audiences are becoming more and more necessary in today's shrinking world. Increasing amounts of learning objects and materials are becoming digital making them more and more accessible within open resources. Providing and using open educational resources allows educators to edit, adapt, and change digital learning objects as needed. Additionally, these resources allow for more flexibility, distribution, and utility. As the global availability of these educational resources increases, the need to consider how to provide cultural affordances increases as well. Several dimensions of affordances will be explored such as language, familiarity or experience, education, cultural, and sub-cultural memberships. Some instances require altering learning objects to the end user and some instances require preparing users to learn more about the global context. A heuristic model is presented here and will show the categories of affordances that should be included when determining the best manners to adapt educational resources to local and global contexts within these varying dimensions.

Resumo: A continua globalização e a necessidade de se localizar materiais para diferentes grupos categoricos estão, cada vez mais, indispensáveis no mundo atual. Um bom número de materiais e de objetos de aprendizagem estão sendo digitalizados, o que os torna mais acessíveis e os recursos muito mais amplos. Oferecendo e utilizando recursos educacionais abertos permitem aos educadores editar, adaptar e mudar objetos digitais de aprendizagem conforme à necessidade. Além disso, esses recursos permitem maior flexibilidade, distribuição e utilização. Com a crescente viabilização global desses recursos de aprendizagem educacionais aumenta-se também a necessidade de se considerar como providenciar tais saliências culturais. Inúmeros aspectos de

saliências culturais serão exploradas como: linguagem, familiaridade ou experiências, educação, grupos cultural ou sub-cultural. Algumas instâncias exigem a alteração de objetos de aprendizagem conforme o usuário, outras exigem a preparação do usuário de acordo com o contexto global. Será apresentada aqui uma tabela modelo que mostrará as categorias de saliências que deverão ser incluídas considerando os recursos educacionais tanto no contexto local quanto global.

Introduction

Education is enhanced when it employs the use of exemplars and simulations. The number of these exemplars and simulations has exploded over the last ten years thanks to the Internet and local digital transmission and storage technologies. Most of these digital artifacts are created by a digitally dominant western nations, or advanced and global economies culture. Access to these digital artifacts by non-western cultures and their desire to consume these artifacts has also grown exponentially in the last ten years. Conversely, members of the American culture are also clamoring to consume artifacts from non-American sources. This creates a challenge to make each of these artifacts consumable by larger audiences.

At first blush, this means language translation, however, making a digital artifact consumable by members of a different culture can require much more than language translation.

Consider Gulliver's Travels. Although an English speaking consumer can read the words, without annotation, the nuance that makes Swift genius is likely lost. Although the need for creating cross-cultural adaptability is growing, the process in varying forms has been around for a long time. The Bible is a prime example. Although bible translations have been around for a long time, many other strategies for broadening its consumption have been employed, and continue to be invented. Current thoughts about the process of creating cultural adaptability consider both altering the object for new consumers, and preparing new consumers to understand the object as it is.

This paper discusses the concepts of culture and sub-cultural influences on the developmental processes of recognizing and acquiring the needed knowledge and abilities to succeed in today's global society. The need to acknowledge and address this change is ever more important. Higher education is attempting to prepare students to learn and work effectively in this international environment. As the global availability of educational resources increases, the need to consider how to provide cultural affordances increases. Several dimensions of affordances will be explored such as language, experience, educational levels, cultural, and sub-cultural membership. The importance of understanding these dimensions assists in the design of the object and presentation of the ideas to the target audience or learners. It is also important to realize that no object is culture free, which is not particularly deleterious, but understanding that any object already has culture and a limited perspective is important to acknowledge.

The appropriateness of the changes can depend on the goals and needs of that particular group. At times teaching a global or new concept to the learners is desired to allow the learners to increase knowledge for the demands of a more globalized economy. Other times it may be more important to modify the object or lesson to the culture or current understanding of the learners or audience. This may occur when the desired outcome is to enrich understanding of the concept by bringing the object closer to the learners' cultural understanding. Many times there are cases where both globalization and localization are occurring for desired outcomes. The heuristic model proposed in this paper is designed to assist in deciding what and how to design learning objects across several criteria.

Before engaging in the discussion of which domains to consider for creating affordances of products or materials across cultures, it can be helpful to review some concepts and definitions as discussed by various theorists and practitioners across several disciplines. Defining and discussing concepts such as globalization, localization, several views of culture, Gibson's affordances and learning to

perceive in new ways will be helpful to understand the concepts for creating cultural affordances. This paper was conceptualized as a way to guide the creation of affordances and the interplay between globalization, localization, and the learning of new ways to perceive.

Globalization

As the world becomes more interdependent economically and politically, it becomes more important to have transferable abilities to navigate more than one culture and even interact with many cultures and ideologies. This interdependence is occurring regardless of whether one acknowledges the shift or not. With the ever increasing access to technology, international media outlets, internet, and social networking, knowledge travels the world almost instantly. Globalization makes an object applicable to a worldwide audience. Globalization is described as "the intensification of worldwide social relations which link distant localities in such a way that local happenings are shaped by events occurring many miles away and vice versa" (Held, 1991, p. 9). Held suggested that globalization is the product of the ever emerging global economy, collective decision making, development of intergovernmental institutions, and continually increasing of global communications (1991). Bringing technology, effective global knowledge, and skills to other locales can be helpful in assisting individuals obtain the skills necessary to access and interact with the global economy. It is also important not to denigrate or destroy culture when bringing global resources to local audiences. The interplay and balance between globalization and localization can be a delicate line to walk.

Localization

In contrast to globalization, localization falls on the other end of the spectrum. Localization can be understood in several ways. The process of localization consists in accommodating a product or service to a specific culture. This

includes the translation of idiomatic expressions, local time, money currency, color interpretation, and men's and women's roles within the culture (Cyr & Trever-Smith, 2004). The Localisation Industry Standards Association (LISA) defines localization as the adaptation of a product or service to meet the local language, cultural, and other expectations of a target population (LISA, 2001). Debry (2001) suggested that localization is adapting a given product, service, material to a specific culture, so it can be easily used by the people in that culture.

Culture

Localization is dependent upon culture and culture specific nuances. Models of culture have traditionally been constructed to explain humanity, explore diverse learners and learning, and provide a framework for cross-cultural analysis, research, and design. These models of culture are multi-disciplinary, dependent on various fields and domains. These domains have conceptualized to contemplate what is known, unknown, and yet to happen. In the field of psychology, researchers formulated models of culture to explain processes of the mind (D'Andrade, 1990; Quinn, 1987; Schank & Abelson, 1977). In anthropology, models of culture take a holistic examination of cultures looking for shared behavior and knowledge (Hall, 1976). Researchers in intercultural communications have designed models of culture to explain value systems, value orientations, and the differences in values across cultures (Condon & Yousef, 1975; Hofstede, 1980). Models of culture in the field of business help personnel to better understand how culture affects management and specifically the impact of cultural values and practices in business (Javidan & House, 2001; Trompenaars & Hampden-Turner, 1998). In the field of instructional design (ID), models of culture focus on integrating culture in the design and development process and on improving learning through culture-based design specifications (Edmundson, 2007b; Henderson, 2007, 1996; Kim; 1999; Lee, 2003; Thomas, Mitchell, &

Joseph, 2002). This multi-disciplinary inquiry suggests that models of culture provide a framework to examine cultures, guide the design of culture-based products and services, and foster cross-cultural communications, relations, and meanings.

A behavioral definition of culture can assist in understanding culture as well. Skinner (1984) explained that "culture may be defined as the contingencies of social reinforcement maintained by a group" (Skinner, 1984, p. 221). Skinner suggested that cultural practices increase the likelihood of survival of that group. As survival increases with the behavior, the contingency to maintain the behavior is strengthened. These shared or common behaviors are important markers of culture as the behaviors are reinforced.

This understanding of culture can help describe the process of acculturation. One way to understand culture is described as "patterns of behavior that are passed from one generation to the next... [and] that serve as the resources for the current life of a social group" (Cole, 2005, p49). Culture is a way of seeing, perceiving, and believing. Gibson (1955) suggested that the ability to perceive or perceptual learning improves with experience and that the acquisition of new knowledge based on the improved ability to perceive. Vygotsky posited that members of every culture teach their children the beliefs and habits they would need as adults, or the psychological tools necessary to succeed in that society (Werstch & Tulviste, 2005). The Vygotskian perspective places a strong emphasis on social interactions and how these interactions influence learning and knowledge that is co-constructed or socially constructed.

Vygotsky's Socio-historical Development

Vygotsky focused his research on the effect of culture and how historical contexts affect mental functioning. Through interactions with parents, peers, schools, and the culture in the community, individuals learn the habits of the mind and cultural tools to succeed (Crain, 2005). According to Vygotsky, the

“shared history, culture, and knowledge shape the thinking and actions” of the individual (Crain, 2005, p. 222). This framework of learning and development is commonly referred to as Socio-historical or Socio-cultural development.

Vygotsky adds that to understand an individual’s learning, one must understand the historical and cultural background of the individual. Not only looking at specific experiences of an individual, but experiences that the culture endures or celebrates together helps comprehend the individual. It is the interaction an individual experiences within his or her own culture that informs and shapes the thoughts, actions, and experience. A child’s parents teach how to act at home and in public. Later, a teacher contributes to what the parents have taught or formalizes the cultural expectations, then peers, and then society continue to shape how one perceives the world and then acts in it. The learning and developing process occurs through the encountering of continually novel concepts (Gredler & Sheilds, 2008).

Rogoff followed Vygotsky’s socio-historical perspective with intercultural subjectivity as she compared values and requirements of a child’s society as shaping culturally adaptive knowledge and skills (Mejia-Arauz, Rogoff, & Paradise, 2005). Culture then, is a social context, socially constructed way of perceiving, learning, and acting. Becoming aware of one’s own culture can also help one recognize and learn about other cultures.

With this view of culture, looking at education, research, or any interaction in the world today cannot be strictly any one culture. Arnett suggested that American Psychology needs to be less American (Arnett, 2008). Arnett’s rationale for this approach includes; Americans only constitute 5% of the world population, research on the whole of humanity is necessary to understand human behavior, and globalization is intensifying (Arnett, 2008, 2002). Arnett continued to suggest that more cultural and international research is needed to be able to generalize findings to a broader audience and to be able to better understand the diversity of humanity and human behavior. Gaining these cultural

sensitivities and competencies are psychological tools that are necessary for today’s global society and economy. As these views of culture are important to understand and acknowledge, it is also necessary to include cultural affordances, or the ways of perceiving, and take into account the ability to learn to perceive in new ways, or understand new or other cultural perspectives.

Gibson’s Affordances

Gibson and Gibson (1955) suggested that perceiving and learning to perceive are important facets of learning. For perception to occur, detection of external stimuli must occur. Sensation is the physical ability to detect stimuli in the environment with the sensory system (visual, auditory, olfactory, haptic, and gustation). Sensation is described as the “reception of stimulation from the environment and the initial encoding of that stimulation into the nervous system” (Ashcraft & Radvansky, 2010, p. 69). As an individual’s senses improve with age, development, and experiencing interaction with one’s environment, the ability to perceive or interpret what one senses also improves and develops. What an individual does with the sensory information, as the brain processes the stimuli is perception. Processing the stimuli with the information sent to the brain from the sensory organs results from improved sensory ability, past experiences, and neurological connections primed by the information are engaged in the process of perception. Perception includes interpreting and understanding sensory information. How one interprets and understands sensation can also be taught by others. Even what information to process, to what one attends, can be influenced by the meaning taught by others. Likewise, as sensation improves, and experience gives meaning to what one senses, perception develops. Berger (2010) describes this interaction of experience (perception) and sensation as follows: “Without experience, newborns stare at lights, startle at noises, and consider every face the same. By six months, they are far more discerning” (Berger, 2010, p. 97).

Gibson's affordances come from the ability to perceive and the learning of how to perceive. Affordances are the interaction of current abilities to perceive and learning new manners to perceive distinguishing features that were not apparent with the previous perceptive abilities (Gibson & Gibson, 1955). This is an ongoing process as the ability to perceive and learning how to interpret constantly interacts in a bi-directional fashion. Experience continues the development of perception. Gibson outlines several concepts that describe the process of learning. Perceptual learning is the process by which an individual learns to perceive (Gibson & Gibson, 1955).

Gibson described affordances as the interaction between the individual's abilities to perceive and the distinguishing features of the environment (Greeno, 1994; Gibson & Gibson, 1955). The process of perceiving is described as "the relationship between an object and an organism that accounts for its utility... affordances [are] one of the primary perceivable aspects of the environment, ... affordances may be among the first properties of the environment differentiated in perceptual development" (Pick, 1992).

The improvement of perceptual learning includes improving the ability to perceive with experience and the acquisition of new knowledge based on the improved ability to perceive. Perceptual development is an important part of cognitive development. Learning and increasing conceptual sophistication comes from increased ability to detect meaningful aspects of external stimuli. Part of how one interprets and assigns meaning to external stimuli comes from what one is taught by others. What may be meaningful to one culture, may not be meaningful to another culture, or can have a completely different meaning.

The interaction between learning to perceive and perceiving is developmental, or that change occurs over time. In the context of learning this means the better we perceive, distinguish, discriminate differences, the better we learn, and learn in new meaningful ways. Perception improves because individuals detect more aspects, features and nuances of the complex stimuli in

the environment, not just because one is rewarded for the new perceptions and differentiations (Gibson & Gibson, 1955; Pick 1992).

Throwing a ball and catching a ball is an example of the interplay of affordances and perceiving. The instructor needs to know the ability of the child, and throw the ball in a way that the student can catch the ball. The student needs to be able to learn to catch the ball, and learn to throw the ball back. At some point the teacher can then throw the ball differently; faster, harder, higher, lower, etc., until the child learns that level of affordance. As the student learns to perceive how to catch better, the difficulty can be increased so the student can learn to perceive at the next level. Performance, or ability to complete task improves and perception of how to perform better improves. This can occur not just because of learning a new way but also an increased ability to perceive. Learning a new language or culture can be like the analogy of learning to throw and catch the ball. Learning ways to interact appropriately in the setting and within the cultural norms need to be successful in intercultural endeavors. Learning a new culture or language is also learning a new way to perceive. Perceiving and learning to perceive new cultures and views of the world can also assist one in understanding one's own culture under a new light. McAllister and Irvine suggested that in order for teachers to be effective with "diverse students, it is crucial that they recognize their own world views" (McAllister & Irvine, 2000, p. 3). Other researchers suggest similar tenets, that understanding or becoming aware of one's own view is paramount to beginning to understand and interact with sensitivity with others' views (Bennett, 1993; Sue, 1982). Multicultural awareness, competency, and appreciation are necessary and advocated by many (Fowers & Davidov, 2006; Sue, Arredondo, & McDavis, 1993; APA 2003).

The remainder of the article includes a discussion of the following facets of creating affordances for various groups and cultures; Learning Objects with Cultural Adaptability, Learning Objects with Multicultural Affordances,

language, direct experience, indirect experience, sub-cultural membership, and modality. Within each row of the table there are several ways to consider that category. Depending on the goals of the creators and end users of the materials, the reasons for choosing one over another can vary.

Loca/Loma within cultural context or ability to adapt	Learning Objects (LO)	Learning Objects with Cultural Adaptability (LOCA)	n - Culture	Learning Objects with Multicultural Affordances (LOMA)	
Language	Indecipherable Language	Proximal Language	Poor Language	Local Language	Universal
Direct Experience (age)	Precise Age	Old Enough	Young Enough	Age Appropriate	Universal
Indirect Experience (Education)	Requires Advanced Education	Requires Esoteric Knowledge	Requires Secondary Education	Requires Basic Literacy and/or Numeracy	Requires No Education
Sub-Cultural Membership	Ethnic Culture	Religious Subculture	Political Subculture	Social Subculture	Universal
Modality	Text Only	Audio File	Still Image	Moving Image	Universal

Table 1

Strategies for Cultural adaptations in Education

Amiel, Squires, and Orey, (2009) suggested several strategies for providing cultural adaptation of learning objects and affordances for diverse cultures; Learning Object with Multicultural Affordances (LOMA), n-Culture, and Learning Objects with Cultural Adaptability. These strategies could be used in other contexts as well. The researchers suggested that learning objects (reusable

digital learning materials) use contextual elements for instruction of targeted learners (Amiel, et al., 2009). Many times these learning objects are published online and others can use it for their own contexts and purposes. The difficulty becomes, as suggested by the authors, how flexible do the learners need to be to come to understand the original context, compared with changing the designed use of the learning object to meet the objectives of the current context. Knowing whether the design should occur within the current cultural context so the recipients can understand within their own vantage point, or whether the desired outcome is to assist the learners to perceive the world in a new way based on another cultural context or vantage point becomes the impetus behind the design of the learning objects. The following table shows a way to visualize what Amiel and colleagues described followed by the definitions and explanations of these facets of design.

LOCA/LOMA Design within cultural context or adaptability to new culture	Learning Objects (LO)	Learning Objects with Cultural Adaptability (LOCA)	n - Culture	Learning Objects with Multicultural Affordances (LOMA)
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Table 2

The LOMA approach instructs the learners in a way that allows learning a more global view. This design enhances the learner's ability to perceive in a new way (outside one's own culture or current understanding). LOMA moves the learner towards the learning object. Amiel and colleagues (2009) suggested that the LOMA approach would allow the instructor or designer of the learning object to ask "what opportunities for teaching about culture does this resource provide" (Amiel, et al., 2009, p 31)? Using the original learning object to teach the cultural context of the learning material is an opportunity to help students understand the original cultural context. The resource can be used to help students perceive in a new way.

The n-Culture approach is a strategy that reduces the need to make affordances for multiple possible culture or subgroup. The designers of the learning object in the n-Culture design come from various cultures, and design the object to be used within each of their sub-cultural groups. This multicultural design team designs the product or object to be used and reused in multiple cultural contexts (Amiel, et al., 2009).

LOCA or Learning Objects with Cultural Adaptability affords the facility of designing the learning object without having to partner with various cultures or contexts in which it might be used. The responsibility for the adaptation falls on the instructor, end designer, or end user to reuse and repurpose the object to fit the needs of the context. The reusability and the ability to repurpose the learning object are implicit in the design. Examples of these resources are akin to Open Educational Resources (OER) (Amiel, et al., 2009). The LOCA design brings the learning object closer to the learner's current level of understanding, or transforms the object to the cultural perception.

These designs and strategies are useful and have specific advantages and disadvantages. Deciding on the design and intended outcome of the objectives of the instructor, designer, and the needs of the learners, assists in the decision to employ either of these strategies. These strategies can be applied outside of education as well in marketing, international and multinational training, corporate training, among other uses. While these strategies are helpful to consider when it is appropriate to either change of a learner's ability to perceive or change the learning object in a way which the student already perceives, it does not address the ways these changes can occur and the facets of the cultural affordances that can be transformed. The remainder of the paper will discuss other strategies that are either included in these strategies or in addition to these four strategies. The following definitions of terms can aid in the conceptualization and employment of these strategies.

Learning Objects (LO) - cultural or contextual design of the learning

materials based on the designer or instructors original culture or viewpoint.

Learning Object with Multicultural Affordances (LOMA) – offers explanations for the learning object and the cultural artifacts or viewpoints within the original learning object.

n-Culture – designing the resource to include the various vantages of the multicultural/multinational design team, designed for repurposing and adapting to the various cultures involved with the project.

Learning Objects with Cultural Adaptability (LOCA) – flexible design for easily adapting and providing affordances for manifold contexts and environments (Amiel, et al., 2009)

Language

Language is a large part of how we perceive the world. We learn language and learn to understand the world differently, and as we learn new ideas we seek to express them through language. Vygotsky (1978) suggested that the cultural line of development is most strongly influenced by language. Others suggest that “language and culture are intimately linked” (DeCapua & Wintergerst, 2010, p. 23). Linguistic relativity is the term that describes the degree to which language influences thought. Whorf's hypothesis (1956) was that thoughts are so influenced by language that language actually determines thought. Where one does not have a word for a concept their thoughts are limited. While many have rejected the absolute application of the hypothesis, it has been moderated to accept that language shapes and influences how one perceives the world. It is not that one cannot learn new words, or a new language, and expand their way of thinking, but that the language one possesses will certainly have an influence upon cognition. When adapting an object to other cultures and places, language has long been considered perhaps the most important aspect of that change. When considering how and what to translate, the following dimensions of

language within the project to get the desired outcome can be helpful. Table three contains definitions which can guide the discussion as to how and what to translate.

Indecipherable Language – Literally, the object includes a language foreign to the user (e.g., Chinese to a native Portuguese-only speaker). This would be the case when a language is written in a completely different writing system such as the differences between Latin or Greek alphabet, Cyrillic as in Slavic and Russian language systems, Sanskrit for Indo-Arabic languages or Kanji as an example of logographic languages and writing systems.

Language	Indecipherable Language	Proximal Language	Poor Language	Local Language	Universal

Table 3

These differences are indecipherable, or could not even be read, by a person that does not speak that language or have some formal school in regard to reading that specific language.

Proximal Language –The object includes a language that is foreign to the user, but relatively understandable (e.g., Spanish to a native Portuguese-only speaker). While many languages have similarities they are different. Sometimes these differences are difficult to overcome, and sometimes there are enough similarities to get some meaning about written texts. This similarity allows some understanding and yet it would still be limited to the extent that one would need to learn the language better to understand more.

Poor Language –The object uses words from the user’s primary language, but their meaning and organization make them barely useful (e.g., Babel fish translation). Many times the object or language is translated into the language but the translation is done poorly. The words are recognizable to the native

speaker, but the meaning is lost. Many times this occurs because the original language has phrases or meanings that do not translate well or the same word may not have all of the possible meanings from one language to another.

Local Language -The object is written in the user’s primary language, but includes reference to local places or local people not known to the user, or colloquial phrases not understood by the user. This design is likely most desirable when the target audience has specific concepts they understand within a local culture. The words may make sense to other speakers of the language but the meaning may not make sense outside of that group or locale.

Universal Language –The object is well written in the user’s primary language and is free of Local Language. The idea with universal language would be remove any local or specific terms that may alienate or favor any one group. This can be the case in Spanish where there are many cultures and nations that speak Spanish. Spanish from Spain is different from Spanish from Mexico, Bolivia, Argentina, Central America, or Caribbean Spanish speaking countries. These regions have large variances in the meanings and colloquialisms from region to region and even within each specific nation or region there is much variability as well. This approach would be a broader approach to reach a larger audience.

To target a more universal approach, Baumann (2008) suggested several important steps for the translation of a project to universally acceptable language to include various subcultures. These steps include: 1) remove regional or common expressions from the text; 2) review and finalize the text before sending it to a translator, and 3) prepare a glossary for a consistent translation (Baumann, 2008). While Baumann suggested these steps in reference to the preparation of marketing materials, the principle underlying her suggestion is that the language needs to carry the same significance for any subculture in the targeted population. Using expressions that have significance for only one of the subcultures in the target population might cause the other subcultures to miss the

message that is being sent, whatever that might be. While the message might have meaning for one group of people, for all of the others it might not. Using more universal terminology should increase the likelihood of reaching every group within a particular culture or set of cultures.

In finalizing text, the preparer should review the material and pay special attention to any cultural-specific vocabulary or other such items that might not pertain to every subculture in the target audience. It may be wise to eliminate these and replace them with more neutral vocabulary. The translator could also be instructed to pay particular attention to the potential for this issue in the translation of the material to avoid the perpetuation of any verbiage that may alienate a part of the target audience (Baumann, 2008).

To target specific local audiences, some suggest localization. Melitz (2008) suggests the need for flexibility when dealing with varying subcultures. This may be especially true owing to the fact that, while language is a “tool of communication” (p. 692), it also reflects other aspects of any given culture as well. One study showed that language can have an impact on the success or failure of the implementation of multilingual marketing websites (Nantel & Glaser, 2008). The quality of the translation of the website into the language of the local target market was shown to impact buyers’ decisions to buy or not to buy from the website. Translating into a localized language allows changes the marketing message to match a specific group. Ricks (1999) recommends hiring local translators rather than American-born language experts. Ricks gave several examples of international translation blunders: In German, "Come alive with Pepsi" was translated clumsily as "Come out' of the grave with Pepsi!" "Body by Fisher" came out as "Corpse by Fisher." In other cases, "car wash" became "Car - enema." One U.S. airline advertised in Brazil that its 747s had rendezvous lounges. To Americans and Frenchmen, rendezvous is one thing. To Portuguese-speaking Brazilians, rendezvous has an illicit meeting.

Direct Experience (age)

Another aspect to consider when localizing a project would be direct experience and the age of the target group. This historical context and shared experience of a group is often called the Cohort Effect. A cohort is a group defined by age. Different age groups share different meanings for events because they experienced and perceived these events together. Because these individuals move through life together they experience and perceive the same events in history as well as the same social movements, and cultural changes that may occur. An example of this would be how different age groups interpret meaning around World War II, the shooting of John F. Kennedy, the Fall of the Berlin Wall, the terrorist attacks on the New York Twin Towers. All of these events have a cohort effect because those with a similar age are more likely to perceive these events and ascribe meaning to these events in a similar manner as others within the cohort. The shared experience is typically influenced by age, one’s peers, and group membership. The following distinctions of age may help one transform a project to the target audience better because the consideration of these ages and groups can enhance the accessibility of the product for the audience.

Direct Experience (age)	Precise Age	Old Enough	Young Enough	Age Appropriate	Universal

Table 4

Precise Age – The object references persons (e.g., one hit wonder), places (e.g., Club 54), or things (e.g., Boogie board), or uses language that only people of a specific age would understand.

Old Enough – The object references persons (e.g., old movie star), places (e.g., route 66), or things (e.g., gas wars), or uses language that only users of a certain age or older would understand.

Young Enough -The object references persons (e.g., current Disney star), places (e.g., the hood), or things (e.g., Bluetooth), or uses language that only users of a certain age or younger would understand.

Age Appropriate -The object references persons, places, or things, or uses language that might be inappropriate for users of a young age.

Universal Age -The object references persons, places, or things, or uses language that is ageless and appropriate for users of all ages.

Deciding whether the content is age appropriate or developmentally appropriate is helpful. To do so, it is necessary to understand the target audience, the ages of potential recipients of the product (end users), or learners of the educational materials. It is also helpful to know what is considered age appropriate in other cultures. It can be offensive if children in a culture are not expected to learn about a taboo topic, or the material may be too difficult based on the target audience as well. Likewise, adolescent or adult learners may also be bored or uninterested with a topic that may be watered down because the original material was intended for a younger audience.

Indirect Experience (education)

Understanding education levels of the students or a target audience is imperative when designing resources. Knowing the literacy levels, ability to use technology, and background knowledge is valuable. Table five shows the facets of education that assist in understanding the learners' education levels when creating affordances for the audience.

UNESCO (2009) estimated that 85% of the world's children have obtained some form of secondary education (grades 7-12). The increase in secondary education at such a high rate is due to the acknowledgment that "secondary education has the transformational ability to change lives forever. . . . For young people all over the world, primary education is no longer enough"

(World Bank, 2005, p. xi-xii). The World Bank also reported that health increases with education as does the reduction of poverty (2005). Knowing the common education levels of a culture, nation, community is an effective strategy for addressing the design of educational materials, a project, or a product. Nearly all the youth in the western hemisphere, east Asia, and Europe are reported to have access to some level of secondary education; 70% in South Asia; and only 40% in sub-Saharan Africa (UNESCO, 2009).

Indirect Experience (Education)	Requires Advanced Education	Requires Esoteric Knowledge	Requires Secondary Education	Requires Basic Literacy and/or Numeracy	Requires No Education
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Table 5

Obtaining an awareness of educational levels, literacy rates, and access to technology is also beneficial. Knowing whether a community or group has an advanced education, esoteric knowledge of specific domains, level of education, or lack of education necessitates examination. Knowing that the intended users or recipients have some secondary education, or very little education would facilitate planning the medium that is most likely useful in that context. The following definitions can assist in determining how to consider differential levels of education.

Advanced –The object references concepts or vocabulary that would exclude most readers without an advanced degree (e.g., statistics).
Esoteric –The object references concepts or vocabulary that would exclude most readers without an esoteric knowledge (e.g., dog breeding). This is a specific domain of knowledge, which may or may not require an advanced degree but certainly would require learning from domain experts or practitioners the manners and language necessary to be included in the group.

Secondary Education –The object references concepts or vocabulary that

would exclude most readers without a high school diploma or some form of secondary education (e.g., World History). The object or materials are outside of the reach of someone with basic literacy or numeracy skills, but within the capacity of comprehension for someone with some secondary education.

Literate –The object uses written language.

No Education –The object is free of written language (e.g., images, YouTube, audio files). This domain may be very difficult to identify and the groups to which one would target may be difficult to access even if identifiable.

Sub-cultural membership

Cultural identity is comprised of several facets including worldview, beliefs, and behavioral practices (Jensen, 2003). Cultural identity would then include religious or moral identity, values, and practices like etiquette pertaining to eating, dressing, work, recreation, expected life transitions within a culture, and other shared beliefs and behaviors amongst the group. Many divisions or sub groups within a culture also have a subculture of expected practices and beliefs. Not all individuals in any one culture may have the same groups or combination of groups. For example, one could be from most nationalities and not share ethnicity, political ideology, or religious beliefs. Using the following heuristic for sub-cultural membership assists in considering the cultural affordances for groups within a culture or sub-culture.

Sub-Cultural Membership	Ethnic Culture	Religious Subculture	Political Subculture	Social Subculture	Universal
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Table 6

The interaction with other groups may also differ. While one group may have certain expectations and beliefs, the exposure to other views and beliefs can influence the acceptance and knowledge of other views. Identifying oneself with

one ethnicity, religion, political ideology, or certain social groups can all interplay with the other groups with which one belongs or interacts. If an individual associates with a social group that is not accepted by one's ethnic or religious group, then a conflict of differing expectations can occur. Subcultural membership can include ethnic identity, religious identity, political ideology, and social groups or associations. Ethnic identity is particularly salient for minority ethnicities within a school, community, or culture (Phinney, 2006; Umana-Taylor, Bhanot, & Shin, 2006). According to Arnett (2010) religious beliefs socialize for three main objectives: "self-regulation, role preparation, and sources of meaning" (2010, p. 105). While industrialized nations are becoming more secular (Bellah, Madsen, Sullivan, Swindler, & Tipton, 1985), religion helps preserve cultural and ethnic traditions, especially in immigrant populations (Peek, 2005), and furthermore some suggest that religious identity is as important or more important than ethnic identity (Sullivan, 2000). Furthermore, different cultures can express or practice the same religion in various ways (Mahmoud, 1996).

Political subculture can be conveyed in terms of political ideology, systems of government, political party affiliation, social identity, and social structures based on ideals of the society the structure represents. Subgroups within any culture may not be apparent to those outside the culture. While diverse and rancorous arguments for political candidates within a nation can be made, outside that nation others may see the candidates as very similar. Within the United States one may be able to discern distinctive features and ideologies between conservative, liberal, and progressive ideas, while onlookers from other nations may see these as fine grades of capitalism and not make such distinctions. Individuals from capitalist nations may have a hard time distinguishing between socialism, and various brands of communism. Nationalism, patriotism, and multiculturalism are also facets of how political identity and subgroups can be considered (Huddy, 2001). Some researchers have found that many ethnic minorities identify more with the national identity firstly, and secondly self-

identify with their ethnic or racial groups (Citrin, Wong, & Duff, 2000; Sears, Citrin, Vindage, & Valentino, 1994).

Some aspects or values may be universal, or that can be applied to all or most cultures. Most times this means that references to specific cultures or groups have been eliminated or not included purposefully to make the product or materials acceptable and useful for all cultures and subcultures.

All of these facets of subcultural membership have an impact on how to approach the adaptation or affordances of design for targeted audiences. Exposure to groups within a society and navigating these groups' differing values can become difficult, let alone having more and more exposure to cultures and subcultures from across the globe adds to the complexity of developing and maintaining identification with any certain group, its values, and expectations (Jensen, 2003). Having at least a working understanding of ethnic majority and minority relations within a region, or differing religious groups within a society is a valuable practice. The following terms and definitions help identify areas of concern when considering how to provide affordances for subcultural membership.

Ethnic –The object references persons, places, things, or activities that are unique to any ethnic cultural not understood by the user.

Religious –The object references persons, places, things, or activities that are unique to any religious culture not understood by the user.

Political –The object references persons, places, things, or activities that are unique to any political cultural not understood by the user.

Social –The object references persons, places, things, or activities that are unique to any social cultural not understood by the user. While this concept is more difficult to define, this could include the macroscopic view of a culture or society. It would likely include ethnic, religious, political, and other interactions

among groups and values within the society. This is more likely to occur in metropolitan societies.

Universal Culture –The object is free of ethnic, religious, political, or social cultural references not understood by the user. This category would be very difficult to find commonalities across all cultures, if not impossible. It may only exist in theory if at all. Although the attempt to make an object as universal as possible or that it could apply to as many cultures as possible. One would be cautioned not to expect that one's own ideas or cultures are how all others do or should perceive or understand the world.

Modality

Another aspect of providing affordances is that of modality. Modality can refer to the mode in which information is created, stored, and disseminated. Consider varying modes of marketing or educational materials that can be adapted to reach audiences not commonly regarded, like individuals with developmental delays or those with visual difficulties, visually impaired, deaf or hard of hearing, or other accessibility challenges. Refer to table seven to view and compare the examples.

A text only document can impede those without vision as well as those that do not speak or read the language from understanding. An audio file precludes those who are deaf or hard of hearing. Still images are also not accessible to the visually impaired. At the same time still images many times do not need translation, unless the context of the image is foreign to the individuals in the target culture.

Modality	Text Only	Audio File	Still Image	Moving Image	Universal

Table 7

Video would limit access for those with visual impairments and would require captioning for the deaf and the hard of hearing. Some objects are more universal or intentionally designed for adapting to various modes of accessibility. The following terms and can assist when considering how one should attend to making allowances for modality.

Text only – Object is not accessible to the blind.

Audio file – Object is not accessible to the deaf.

Still image – Object is not accessible to the blind.

Moving Image – Object might have limited access to the blind and requires captioning for deaf.

Universal – Object meets universal accessibility requirements.

Conclusion

These aspects and components of the affordance process can support the reasoning behind how and when one makes decisions regarding the globalization and localization. There are times when more localization makes sense, and others when more globalization suits the goals of the project or product. Depending the goals and purposes of the initiative, and considering the factors outlined, bringing the individual targeted the materials in a way in which he or she can best understand or creating the most culturally affordable object can be helpful. If the desired outcome is to educate the recipient regarding the global context, the increasing the ability to perceive at the global level would be advantageous.

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